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M5.8 - Pilot for Exposing Repository Trustworthiness Status and FAIR Data and Code Assessment Outcomes in Generic and Disciplinary Registries and Portals

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TERMINOLOGY

Also see the Appendix for an overview of several data services and their acronyms.

Terminology/Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CoreTrustSeal	Certification body for Trustworthy Digital Repositories
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services, one of the project partners
Dataverse	An open source research data repository software. DataverseNL refers to a research data repository co-provided by DANS and participating institutions.
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile
dct	Property prefix related to the DCMI Metadata Terms
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
DRAWG	Data Repository Attribute Working Group.
EARL	Evaluation and Report Language
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
EVAL	Evaluation Result Ontology
F-UJI	Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAIR4RS	FAIR principles for Research Software
FAIRiCAT	FAIR Interoperability Catalogue
FAIRsFAIR	A Horizon 2020 project focused on Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe that ran from 2019-2022
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
foaf	Friend of a Friend vocabulary
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	A Linked Data method for JSON
oa	Open Annotation
OSTrails	Open Science Trails, a Horizon Europe project focused on delivering the commons to plan-track-assess research in EOSC.
PID	Persistent Identifier
QMO	Quality Model Ontology
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
re3data	Registry of Research Data Repositories, one of the project partners
schema.org	A vocabulary consisting of a set of extensible schemas
TEST	Test Metadata Vocabulary
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
vcard	Ontology for describing People and Organizations
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

1.1 Role of the milestone

The purpose of this Milestone is to provide a progress report on the prototype development, embodying FAIR-IMPACT's approach to implementing the principles outlined in the initial version of the *"Guidelines for repositories and registries on exposing repository trustworthiness status and FAIR data assessments outcomes"*¹ (Milestone 5.2).

The proposed standards and technology stack are based on insights gathered through the activities in the earlier project FAIRsFAIR "Fostering FAIR Data Practices In Europe"² and cross-work package collaboration and exchange among the FAIR-IMPACT project partners. This application of this stack is aimed at complementing the guidelines' technology and tool-agnostic character by establishing an initial linking and information structure for the prototype to be developed. It is intended to bridge repositories with registries and discovery services, thereby facilitating the better exposure and discovery of repository information. The registry role within the prototype will be covered both by re3data - registry of research data repositories, as well as DANS.³

In addition, the prototype will enable the provision of information on the object level as well as quality measures due to the extensibility of the chosen technology stack. This work will serve as the foundation for the development of future guideline versions. Suggestions collected from the community will be used for revising, extending, and refining the transparent exposure of repository information and its support in registries, like re3data, as well as other services, such as F-UJI⁴ and CoreTrustSeal⁵. Thus the approach is similar to the development of the guidelines and ensures that not only the prototype but also the guidelines themselves remain responsive to the needs and insights of stakeholders.

1.2 Means of verification

The means of verification for this Milestone is to have a report available detailing the Milestone. The current document establishes this verification, and is made publicly available on Zenodo.

¹ Verburg, M., Ulrich, R., L'Hours, H., Huber, R., Priddy, M., Davidson, J., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Meijas, G., & Neidiger, C. (2023). M5.2 - Guidelines for repositories and registries on exposing repository trustworthiness status and FAIR data assessments outcomes (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10058634>

² <https://fairsfair.eu/>

³ <https://www.re3data.org/>, <https://dans.knaw.nl/nl/>

⁴ Anusuriya Devaraju, & Robert Huber. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400>

⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

2 Description of the Milestone

2.1 Architecture and Pilot Design

The overall architecture of the prototype has been explained in detail in Milestone M5.5 “Initial repository registry support for discovery of repositories, policies, and interfaces”⁶. The overall abstract model was based on the assumption that trustworthiness requires transparency so that repositories that claim characteristics and involved processes are assessed by validation services or authorities to verify those claims (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - The main interactions of relevance to the guidelines and prototype.

In this Deliverable, the basic architecture has been agreed on and the decision has been made to use basic RDF⁷, which allows for the presentation of information in ways that are understandable to both human actors and machine agents. To enable exploration of (meta)data services, the use of schema.org⁸ or DCAT^{9,10} has been recommended since DCAT is an established and matured standard and recommended by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). To expose quality information such as certificates of FAIR assessment results the use of the Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV)¹¹ was proposed which also is part of the W3C data on the web family of standards. This is the reference framework for the architecture of the prototype and the recommendations described below to expose repository information.

A major design principle of the architecture is to expose information at the source of its origin. This allows for a current and accurate exposure by the primary data provider. Furthermore, the architecture is focusing on linking data and breaking up information silos.

⁶ Ulrich, R., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., Huber, R., L'Hours, H., Neidiger, C., Meijas, G., & Davidson, J. (2023). M5.5 - Initial repository registry support for discovery of repositories, policies, and interfaces (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10847707>

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

⁸ <https://schema.org/>

⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

¹⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

¹¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv>

Both principles combined enable a simple structure for validation. As an example, a repository may expose its certification and link directly to the certification provided by the validation authority. This enables data consumers, e.g. technical infrastructures or humans, to follow the links, gather further details, and validate the given information.

Early 2024 the RDA data repository attributes working group (DRAWG)¹² published the RDA Common Descriptive Attributes of Research Data Repositories¹³ which allows focus on a small set of relevant repository metadata properties. In the following sections we use the DRAWG attributes as a basis for modelling repository metadata using DCAT and DQV. As schema.org is also frequently used in practice to convey metadata in addition to DCAT, we will also discuss this below.

The provision of subject-specific information is challenging as it requires specialisation in the formats and interfaces, which cannot be provided in generic registries and infrastructures with a broad subject coverage. This issue is addressed by the decentralised and extensible characteristic of the architecture. RDF follows an open world assumption and allows additional information to be exposed. Moreover, many RDF vocabularies such as DCAT allow for extensions. As an example, a repository from the earth and space sciences can expose subject specific data via GeoDCAT¹⁴ and the described DataService¹⁵. General registries can still parse the core information, yet subject-specific registries are able to gather data that is required, for instance to query for locations or to display maps.

2.1.1 The Pilot

To demonstrate the practical implementation of this architecture we designed a pilot implementation which consists of a mixture of existing infrastructures as well as prototypic implementations representing the interplay between data repositories, digital objects (datasets and software), registries, validation authorities, and tools (related to trustworthiness and FAIRness).

For those newly developed pilot tools and services, a dedicated public Github repository has been created¹⁶.

2.1.2 Validation and Assessment

With respect to validation, the pilot builds on existing validation authorities and assessment tools, for example CoreTrustSeal for trustworthiness as well as the F-UJI Automated FAIR

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rationale/data-repository-attributes-wg/>

¹³ Witt, M., Cannon, M., Lister, A., Segundo, W., Shearer, K., Yamaji, K., & Research Data Alliance Data Repository Attributes Working Group. (2024). RDA Common Descriptive Attributes of Research Data Repositories (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00103>

¹⁴ <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/>

¹⁵ https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/#Class:Data_Service

¹⁶ https://github.com/FAIRsFAIR/5_4_prototype

Data Assessment Tool¹⁷ FAIRness and the newly developed F-UJI version^{18,19} which is able to test metrics based on the FAIR4RS principles²⁰. For both FAIR and trustworthiness validation, the currently used repositories for assessment and certification results can be found respectively at F-UJI²¹ and the dedicated Dataverse for CoreTrustSeal²² hosted by DataverseNL. Both serve as real life examples on how metadata for certificates and assessment results may be expressed and exposed as described further in the Milestone.

2.1.3 Registries

The pilot further uses the established registry from re3data and is investigating to support further registries by providing dedicated catalogue metadata harvesting services. A first version of such a harvester has been developed and is publicly available²³. Re3data maps essential metadata properties as defined by RDA DRAWG within the context of catalogue metadata exposure and harvesting.

2.1.4 Repositories

In addition to the many data repositories and their data objects which are use case partners of FAIR-IMPACT²⁴, we set up a prototype repository²⁵ (Figure 2) which can be used to test the concepts described above without disturbing the operational systems of our use case partners. This prototype repository consists of a simple web based repository homepage as well as an integrated catalogue which contains a single test dataset. The repository provides DCAT as well as schema.org catalogue metadata compliant to the DRAWG specifications explained in detail below. The prototype repository webpage is publicly available and the source code of the prototype repository is available at Github²⁶.

¹⁷ Anusuriya Devaraju, & Robert Huber. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400>

¹⁸ Moraw, K., Antonioletti, M., Breitmoser, E., Chue Hong, N., & Priddy, M. (2024). M5.6 - Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10890043>

¹⁹ This version of F-UJI is currently available at <http://scraper.software.ac.uk/index.php> until October 2024. For more information see: <https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-1-assessment-and-improvement-research-software>

²⁰ Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. et al. Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. Sci Data 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>

²¹ <https://f-ujii.net/results>

²² <https://dataverse.nl/dataverse/coretrustseal>

²³ https://github.com/FAIRsFAIR/5_4_prototype/tree/main/harvester

²⁴ <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases>

²⁵ <https://dummyrepository.org>

²⁶ https://github.com/FAIRsFAIR/5_4_prototype

Figure 2 - Screenshot of the prototype repository at <https://dummyrepository.org>

2.1.5 Digital Objects

In addition to the data object contained within the prototype repository, several digital object types which are part of the pilot are involved. For example, the FAIR assessment results and CoreTrustSeal certificates are available via the aforementioned public repositories as digital objects. Further digital objects which are considered within the pilot are registry and catalogue entries. The work on the pilot therefore also involves considerations about how to expose metadata of these object types in DCAT or schema.org which is described below. Table 1 summarises our initial approach.

Table 1 - Proposed resource types which may be used to identify digital objects involved in the pilot.

	DCAT	schema.org
FAIR assessment results	dqv:QualityMetadata, dcat:Dataset	schema:contentRating, schema:Dataset

Registry records	dcatalog:Catalog / dcat:Dataset ²⁷	schema:Dataset
Catalogue record	dcatalog:Dataset	schema:Dataset
Certificates	dqv:QualityCertificate	schema:Certificate

2.2 Exposure and Harvesting of Repository Information

Using the pilot architecture and design described above and adhering to the aforementioned guidelines, we have drafted descriptions and recommendations for exposing repository information. This section of the Milestone will depict how several specific instances of information could be exposed, including examples and mappings of schemas to the relevant DRAWG attributes.

2.2.1 Exposing Repository Information with DCAT

We follow the definition of data repository given by DCAT-AP²⁸ “a catalogue or repository that hosts the Datasets or Data Services being described.” and therefore model a repository as an instance of dcat:Catalog. To indicate the operational and organisational nature of a data repository we recommend to additionally use foaf:Project and/or foaf:Organisation for each instance of a data repository.

2.2.1.1 Descriptive Metadata

To provide basic descriptive metadata corresponding to DRAWG properties the use of DCAT properties as well as Dublin Core terms²⁹ is recommended. In addition, friend of a friend (foaf) properties³⁰ can be used in case catalogue instances are modelled as foaf:Project or foaf:Organization.

Most of these properties will be provided as Literals. However, we follow the recommendation of DCAT-AP to use instances of foaf:Agent (here foaf:Organization) for dcat:publisher values. In addition, vcard:Organization³¹ should be used as type for dcat:publisher. This allows to include address information such as country name, which is required to provide DRAWG’s ‘Country’ property info.

Table 2 - Mapping of different DRAWG attributes to recommended properties.

²⁷ [see 2.1.6 Cascaded Harvesting] Ulrich, R., Verburg, M., Priddy, M., Huber, R., L'Hours, H., Neidiger, C., Meijas, G., & Davidson, J. (2024). M5.5 - Initial repository registry support for discovery of repositories, policies, and interfaces (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10847707>

²⁸ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.0/#Catalogue>

²⁹ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

³⁰ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

³¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vcard-rdf/>

DRAWG	schema.org
Repository Name	dct:title (foaf:name)
URL	dct:identifier (foaf:homepage)
Description	dct:description
Language	dct:language
Research Area	dcat:theme or dct:subject
Organisation	dct:publisher (a foaf:Organization, vcard:Organization)
Country	dct:publisher (a vcard:Organization) => vcard:country-name
Dataset Use License	dct:license
Terms of Access	dct:accessRights
Contact	dcat:contactPoint

2.2.1.2 Supported Standards

To expose information about standards offered to support machine interoperability, we recommend using `dcat:service` which allows us to provide a list of instances of `dcat:DataService`. There, the properties `dcat:endpointURL` and `dct:conformsTo` shall be used to provide information about the service endpoint URL as well as the service type which should be the web link to the documentation of the standard the web API follows (see the Appendix and the living document³²).

```
dcat:service: [
- {
  @type: "dcat:DataService",
  dcat:endpointURL: "https://dummyrepository.org/.well-known/api-catalog",
  dct:conformsTo: "https://signposting.org/FAIRiCat/"
},
```

Figure 3 - Example of `dcat:service` use

Supported standards which do not represent actionable services can be expressed using the

³² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1mfVK5kEqTCi67R-6bmDj4-qfvi2pPHdLFnL-hqvZqEE/edit?gid=0#gid=0>

dct:conformsTo property which shall point to an instance of dct:Standard. The property rdfs:seeAlso may be used to additionally indicate which standard type is listed. Here we recommend to use the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) vocabulary³³.

To unambiguously identify a metadata standard we recommend to use a linked term from either the DCC metadata list³⁴ or from FAIRsharing³⁵. In case a XML standard is used the namespace identifier can also be used.

To indicate supported persistent identifier (PID) types, we recommend using the home URI of a PID system (e.g. DOI³⁶, Handle³⁷, etc.), which uniquely identifies a PID system.

```
dct:conformsTo: [
  + { ... },
  + { ... },
  - {
    @type: "dct:Standard",
    @id: "http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/dcat-data-catalog-vocabulary",
    rdfs:seeAlso: "https://w3id.org/fair/fip/latest/Metadata-schema"
  },
  - {
    @type: "dct:Standard",
    @id: "https://w3id.org",
    rdfs:seeAlso: "https://w3id.org/fair/fip/latest/Identifier-service"
  }
],
```

Figure 4 - Example of persistent identifier type exposure

2.2.1.3 Policies and Principles

Similar to the way we recommend to indicate standards, the dct:conformsTo property should be used to link an instance of dct:Policy or subclasses of dct:Policy. Here we recommend to use dct:accrualPolicy to indicate documents which describe the terms of deposit and the premis:PreservationPolicy³⁸ to indicate the preservation and/or curation policy of a data repository.

Table 3 - Mapping of dct:conformsTo to other properties for different DRAWG attributes.

DRAWG	schema.org
--------------	-------------------

³³ <https://w3id.org/fair/fip/>

³⁴ <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards>

³⁵ <https://fairsharing.org>

³⁶ <https://doi.org>

³⁷ <https://handle.net>

³⁸ <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/>

Curation	dct:conformsTo => dct:Policy or premis:PreservationPolicy
Terms of Deposit	dct:conformsTo => dct:accrualPolicy
Preservation	dct:conformsTo => premis:PreservationPolicy

```
dct:conformsTo: [
- {
  @type: "dct:accrualPolicy",
  @id: "https://dummyrepository.org/policies/termsofdeposit.html"
},
- {
  @type: "premis:PreservationPolicy",
  @id: "https://dummyrepository.org/policies/preservationpolicy.html",
  rdfs:seeAlso: "https://w3id.org/fair/fip/latest/Metadata-preservation-policy"
},
]
```

Figure 5 - Example of policy exposure

2.2.1.4 Certification and Quality Information

The Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV) is part of the W3C data on the web best practices family of standards and recommended to be used within DCAT to indicate quality assessments and certificates. Therefore, we recommend to use the `dqv:hasQualityAnnotation` to indicate an instance of `dqv:QualityCertificate`, which links e.g. a `CoreTrustSeal` certificate of a data repository. The issuer of such a certificate can be indicated using the `dc:creator` property. The certificate itself has to be contained via a `oa:hasBody`³⁹ property since a `dqv:QualityCertificate` is a subclass of `oa:Annotation`. There, we recommend to use the DOI of a `CoreTrustSeal` certificate which is not shown in the example below (Figure 6).

Table 4 - Mapping of DRAWG attribute to properties.

DRAWG	schema.org
Certification	<code>dqv:hasQualityAnnotation =></code> <code>dqv:QualityCertificate</code>

³⁹ <https://www.w3.org/community/openannotation/>


```
- dqv:hasQualityAnnotation: {
  @type: "dqv:QualityCertificate",
  dct:creator: "CoreTrustSeal",
  oa:hasTarget: "https://dummyrepository.org",
  oa:hasBody: "https://amt.coretrustseal.org/certificates",
  oa:motivatedBy: "dqv:qualityAssessment"
},
```

Figure 6 - Example of certificate exposure

2.2.2 Exposing Repository Information with schema.org

Unlike ESIP’s model⁴⁰, which defines a data repository as an instance of schema:Organization, schema:ResearchProject, and schema:Service, we model a data repository (or at least the operational part of a data repository) simply as an instance of schema:Project and schema:DataCatalog. We chose schema:Project instead of schema:ResearchProject because a data repository usually does not perform research as the main purpose. Since every data repository should also have a catalogue of its datasets, we propose to use schema:DataCatalog in addition to schema:Project. If a data repository is an independent organisational or legal entity, schema:Organization can optionally be used as an additional type or in replacement of schema:Project to model a data repository. These schema.org types allow us to describe all essential DRAWG properties which we propose to map to schema.org as follows.

2.2.2.1 Descriptive Metadata

Since schema:DataCatalog is a subtype of schema:CreativeWork some descriptive properties are available which easily can be mapped to DRAWG.

Table 5 - Mapping of DRAWG attributes to schema.org properties.

DRAWG	schema.org
Repository Name	schema:name
URL	schema:url
Description	schema:description
Language	schema:inLanguage
Research Area	schema:keywords

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/ESIPFed/science-on-schema.org/blob/main/guides/DataRepository.md>

Organization	schema:publisher
Country	schema:publisher >= schema:address => schema:addressCountry
Dataset Use License	schema:license
Terms of Access	schema:conditionsOfAccess
Contact	schema:contactPoint

For the schema.org keywords property, it is possible to use the type schema:DefinedTerm which allows to use ontology terms unambiguously specifying research areas. Since the DRAWG property ‘Country’ is defined as *“The country in which the repository operates”*, we map this DRAWG property to the country information (schema:addressCountry) contained in a schema:publisher’s schema:address property.

To indicate the contact information for a given repository we recommend to use the schema:contactPoint property which is part of schema:Project and allows to include detailed schema:ContactPoint properties such as phone, email, fax etc.

2.2.2.2 Supported Standards

To expose information of available APIs supporting machine interoperability of a data repository, we propose to use the schema:offers property, which may list several instances of schema:Offer, which then links to instances of schema:WebAPI (a subclass of schema:Service) via their schema:itemOffered property. There, we follow the example of FAIRiCAT⁴¹ and use the schema:documentation to describe the type of service. This should be the web link to the documentation of the standard the web API follows. The schema:url can be used to describe the endpoint URI of the API.

```
{
  @type: "schema:Offer",
  - schema:itemOffered: {
    @type: "schema:WebAPI",
    schema:url: "https://dummyrepository.org/services/static_oai.xml",
    schema:documentation: "https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/guidelines-static-repository.htm"
  }
},
```

Figure 7 - Example of exposure of available APIs

An initial list of web APIs and their documentation links can be found in Appendix 1.

⁴¹ <https://signposting.org/FAIRiCat>

Similarly, other standards supported by a data repository can be described using schema.org as an schema:Offer, which then should be a schema:Service instead of a schema:WebAPI. We propose to use the property schema:serviceType to unambiguously indicate which DRAWG service category (persistent identifier or metadata standard) is described. We recommend using the FAIR vocabulary terms Identifier Service⁴² and Metadata Schema⁴³ respectively to do so.

```
{
  @type: "schema:Offer",
  - schema:itemOffered: {
    @type: "schema:Service",
    schema:documentation: "http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/dcat-data-catalog-vocabulary",
    schema:serviceType: "https://w3id.org/fair/fip/latest/Identifier-service"
  }
},
```

Figure 8 - Example of standards exposure

Again, we use the schema:documentation to indicate the PID or metadata standard a data repository supports.

Similarly as mentioned in the previous section, to indicate supported persistent identifier (PID) types, we recommend using the home URI of a PID system (e.g. DOI⁴⁴, Handle⁴⁵, etc.), which uniquely identifies a PID system.

For metadata standards, we recommend unique identifiers such as a FAIRsharing identifier (DOI), a DCC identifier, or the unique namespace or schema URI of e.g. XML metadata standards.

Table 6 - Mapping of DRAWG attributes to schema.org properties.

DRAWG	schema.org
Machine Interoperability	Schema:offers => schema:Offer => itemOffered => schema:WebAPI
Persistent Identifiers	Schema:offers => schema:Offer => itemOffered => schema:Service
Metadata	Schema:offers => schema:Offer => itemOffered => schema:Service

⁴² <https://w3id.org/fair/fip/latest/Identifier-service>
⁴³ <https://w3id.org/fair/fip/latest/Metadata-schema>
⁴⁴ <https://doi.org>
⁴⁵ <https://handle.net>

2.2.2.3 Policies and Principles

Unfortunately, schema.org does not offer a generic way to describe policies such as dc:Policy via dc:conformsTo. However, schema:DataCatalog inherited the schema:publishingPrinciples from schema:CreativeWork which may serve to point to “a document describing the editorial principles”, which therefore is well suited to link to DRAWG terms of deposit etc.. We include the DRAWG ‘Curation’ property here because it may be explained in a dedicated data curation policy document.

Table 7 - Mapping of schema:publishingPrinciples to several DRAWG attributes.

DRAWG	schema.org
Curation	schema:publishingPrinciples
Terms of Deposit	schema:publishingPrinciples
Preservation	schema:publishingPrinciples

To clarify which policy actually is described, we recommend to use the schema:additionalType property and here to use the values premis:PreservationPolicy to indicate the preservation policy and dct:accrualPolicy to indicate the terms of deposit.

```
schema:publishingPrinciples: [
- {
  @type: "schema:CreativeWork",
  schema:url: "https://dummyrepository.org/policies/termsofdeposit.html",
  schema:additionalType: "dct:accrualPolicy"
},
```

Figure 9 - Example of exposure of policy

2.2.2.4 Certification and Quality Information

As mentioned above, we chose schema:Project to model a data repository which allows us to include additional DRAWG properties. From these, we recommend to use the schema:hasCertification property to indicate certification details such as a given CoreTrustSeal certification. This property requires the use of a schema:Certification instance which allows linking to a certification document via the schema:url property which should be the DOI of a CoreTrustSeal certificate. It further allows to include useful information about certificates such as audit date, validity and issuer.

```

schema:hasCertification: {
  @type: "schema:Certification",
  schema:url: "https://amt.coretrustseal.org/certificates",
  schema:certificationStatus: "schema:CertificationActive",
  - schema:issuedBy: {
    @type: "schema:Organization",
    schema:name: "CoreTrustSeal",
    schema:url: "https://www.coretrustseal.org"
  },
  schema:auditDate: "2024-09-09",
  schema:expires: "2024-12-31"
},

```

Figure 10 - Example of exposure of certification information

Table 8 - Mapping of DRAWG certification attributes to schema.org properties.

DRAWG	schema.org
Certification	schema:hasCertification
Contact	schema:contactPoint

In addition, the use of schema:Project this would allow information about funding sources and other useful things which are relevant for the scientific community.

2.2.3 Exposing Repository Affordances with FAIRiCAT

FAIRiCat⁴⁶ is an emerging specification for encoding machine-actionable information about services and features offered by a repository ('affordances') in a standardised way. It does so by either by providing a link to such information in the header of a URL typically associated with a repository website, or by providing a URL (via the .well-known URL address) that resolves directly to the information. This allows automated mechanisms to predictably discover machine-actionable information about the repository.

FAIRiCat provides the affordances information via a JSON Linkset document (application/linkset+json), and the Linkset, in turn, contains an element (anchor) for each 'affordance' that one wishes to expose. For each anchor element, a minimum set of

⁴⁶ <https://signposting.org/FAIRiCat/#linkset>

sub-elements are documented: the full URL to a resource or service, the machine-readable specification for or description of the service, and an optional human-readable specification or description of the resource.

To accommodate the typical information envisaged in DRAWG, one would have the following implementation options:

- Creating a single entry in the Linkset that points to e.g. the DCAT record of repository properties, features, and services. This takes care of automated services that implement the specifications proposed in this document.
- Creating a Linkset as defined in FAIRiCat, reflecting the scope of services and properties defined by DRAWG, with an additional service that offers the same information encoded as a DCAT document. This approach is potentially more cumbersome, but retains compatibility with FAIRiCat implementations.

Creating a simple utility application - a user interface and the ability to consume, edit, and export both FAIRiCat Linkset documents and DCAT documents, as envisaged for the prototype - will ensure that Linksets and DCAT documents are interchangeable, quality assured, and available for either implementation option.

2.2.3.1 Findability of Repository Metadata - Protocols and Standards

Information harvesters and robots expect metadata directly at the location to which a persistent or unique identifier refers. Today, a comparatively small number of methods are used for this purpose:

Embedding metadata: machine-readable metadata is embedded in the source code of an identifier's human-friendly target page. Microdata, RDFa, meta-tags or embedded JSON-LD can be used for this purpose. Of these formats, JSON-LD has prevailed in recent years (Fig. 3), which is due to the support of most major search engines for this format.

Typed links and signposting: with this method, typed links are embedded in the source code or in the response header information of a web page. In addition to the file format offered, specific metadata standards can also be specified. This allows the client to immediately recognize which content is available, thus specific, targeted requests are possible.

Content negotiation: For this purpose, basic web standards of the HTTP protocol are used, which allow specific response formats to be requested via sent header information. Without further knowledge of the server's offerings, however, this always requires a request to the server, which can also fail.

Figure 11 - Number of domains vs. metadata formats found in webdatacommons crawls⁴⁷

For the output of repository metadata, we recommend the use of JSON-LD as a serialisation format and two offering methods:

- **Embedding JSON-LD metadata** in the source code of web pages. As described above, both schema.org and DCAT metadata can be used for this purpose.
- **Typed links leading to JSON-LD** formatted metadata.

For both methods, schema.org or DCAT should be used to offer repository metadata.

2.3 Trust through Transparency - Certification and beyond

An underlying assumption of this work is that trustworthiness depends on transparency about the characteristics of digital objects and repositories (including any assessment outcomes and certification status). These characteristics may be more or less machine actionable, ranging from free text metadata values (contact email), to selections from ontologies (domain/disciplines), to less structured information artefacts such as policy documents (preservation policy). For digital objects, transparent information would include that which is necessary to perform an assessment of FAIRness, as well as the outcomes of those assessments. For repositories and other data and metadata services, transparent information would be related to a wide range of activities and functions⁴⁸. To avoid duplication and to ensure currency it is proposed that repositories should expose information about themselves and the digital objects they hold. This information can then be harvested by third parties for a variety of purposes, including repository registries (e.g.

⁴⁷ <https://webdatacommons.org/structureddata/#results-2023-1>

⁴⁸ L'Hours, H., & Bell, D. (2023). Repository & (Meta)Data Services Activities & Functions Overview (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689090>

re3data, FAIRsharing) and certification service providers (CoreTrustSeal⁴⁹). Directly accessing transparent information from a repository at source is an enabler of trustworthiness but is not in itself sufficient.

Some information can be subject to testing and validation. Claims of certification status may be validated via a third party (e.g. CoreTrustSeal certification⁵⁰) and claims could be supported by a certification API and/or the presence of a certificate at a provided URL. Other information may be amenable to direct testing e.g. an email address is well-formed, a URL resolves, a keyword is from a declared semantic artefact or a link to an XML file validates a declared schema.

It is inevitable that some tests and validations will fail, and essential that repositories understand the reason for failure and what remedial actions are indicated⁵¹. In some examples the test may be at fault, so feedback loops to correct the test and associated metrics should be in place. In other cases the test tool may not be able to find or interpret information which does exist; this may imply actions by the tool developer to widen their resource discovery parameters, or actions by the information provider to expose information in a more machine-friendly way.

It remains true that much information of value is mainly available in less structured prose artefacts such as policies and procedures, which are less machine interpretable. In some cases such as levels of curation and preservation⁵² we can begin to identify relevant metadata to enable machines⁵³. But it is important that we don't devalue and ignore prose information as transparent sharing remains critical to humans seeking to learn and understand the practices of their peers. Assessment and certification processes such as CoreTrustSeal could be made more efficient and reliable by machines actionable testing of assertions exposed by repositories, but for the foreseeable future the wide range of repository practices and resources will often be exposed through prose statements that are best interpreted by human experts. So, in addition to the remedial issues described above to adjust information exposure, metrics and tests, there remains a need for support and guidance on repository practice and digital object outcomes (see the section on Guidance, below).

As noted above, the initial prototype focusses on a small set of relevant repository metadata properties indicated by the DRAWG. Beyond this there is significant scope to expand these mechanisms to support both humans and machines in a wider variety of use cases.

For machines, we envisage improving the labelling (typing) of the published certificates so that it is immediately clear to machines what they are. For example, as mentioned above, the metadata of CoreTrustSeal certificates published at DataverseNL that is usually published as an instance of schema:Dataset could also be labelled as an instance of schema:Certificate.

⁴⁹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://amt.coretrustseal.org/certificates>

⁵¹ L'Hours, H., & Bell, D. (2024). Generic Assessment & Evaluation Reference Model. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13134535>

⁵² CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2024). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

⁵³ L'Hours, H., Kleemola, M., & Recker, J. (2024). CoreTrustSeal Levels of Curation and Preservation: Implied Repository and Object Metadata Characteristics (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12701324>

2.4 Exposing Digital Object Assessment Results

2.4.1 Data(set) assessment

FAIR assessment results stored in a repository or database are themselves an important digital resource. It is therefore important to take sufficient care to make them FAIR. FAIR results should therefore be made transparent for both humans and machines. Common embeddable metadata standards, such as schema.org or DCAT as JSON-LD, are suitable for this purpose. We recommend storing FAIR results expressed as schema.org as instances of schema:Dataset and schema:Rating, results provided as DCAT should be instances of dcat:Dataset and dqv:QualityMetadata. This pragmatic approach is currently being tested in the pilot in a test instance of F-UJI. Assessed datasets may indicate such a FAIR assessment result within their metadata using the schema.org property schema:contentRating using the URI of the assessment result to be referenced. For humans, FAIR badges may additionally be used which are already offered by F-UJI as already described in detail in FAIRsFAIR deliverable D4.5⁵⁴.

2.4.2 Software assessment

Work in FAIR-IMPACT's Task 4.3 and 5.2 defined guidance for software metadata (D4.4)⁵⁵ and FAIR software metrics (D5.2)⁵⁶, as well as implementing some of these metrics as practical tests in F-UJI (M5.6)⁵⁷. Historically, assessment of data has focussed on repositories and datasets, whereas assessment of software can be applied to producers, projects or products⁵⁸. The expansion of the concepts of repository trustworthiness and FAIR assessment to software can be considered both independently and dependent on each other.

Trustworthiness, e.g. as measured by CoreTrustSeal, has many overlapping characteristics for data and software, such as plans and procedures around confidentiality, data integrity, continuity of access, and preservation; adequate organisational, technical and security infrastructure; and metadata and APIs to enable discoverability. If a repository, either a digital repository or code repository/forg, adheres to these requirements, it can be considered trustworthy for software as well. A key difference is the way that quality should be assessed, and the practicalities of how this will be done. With data, it may be sufficient for quality to be assessed only at the time of deposit, but for software quality, particularly reusability, may change with time due to the greater number of dependencies.

⁵⁴ Huber, Robert, Cepinskas, Linas, Davidson, Joy, Herterich, Patricia, L'Hours, Hervé, Mokrane, Mustapha, von Stein, Ilona, & Verburg, Maaïke. (2021). D4.5 Report on FAIR Data Assessment Toolset and Badging Scheme <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336159>

⁵⁵ Gruenpeter, M., Granger, S., Monteil, A., Chue Hong, N., Breitmoser, E., Antonioletti, M., Garijo, D., González Guardia, E., Gonzalez Beltran, A., Goble, C., Soiland-Reyes, S., Juty, N., & Mejias, G. (2024). D4.4 - Guidelines for recommended metadata standard for research software within EOSC (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10786147>

⁵⁶ Chue Hong, N., Breitmoser, E., Antonioletti, M., Davidson, J., Garijo, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gruenpeter, M., Huber, R., Jonquet, C., Priddy, M., Shepherdson, J., Verburg, M., & Wood, C. (2023). D5.2 - Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0 - DRAFT not yet approved by the European Commission). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047401>

⁵⁷ Moraw, K., Antonioletti, M., Breitmoser, E., Chue Hong, N., & Priddy, M. (2024). M5.6 - Practical tests for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10890043>

⁵⁸ Where might software fit with CoreTrustSeal? (2017) <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.5426935.v1>

The approach taken by FAIR assessment tools so far has been at the dataset or code repository level, and software assessment has been at the level of a project residing in a code repository. This could be extended to assess software source code for a project that has been deposited in a digital repository, both at deposit (as mandated by the repository) and as required (by potential users of the software). How this might be integrated into existing repository management infrastructure has not been sufficiently explored at present.

2.4.3 Harmonising Assessment Outputs

Since there are currently several FAIR assessment tools that deal with different aspects of FAIR and that specialise in different digital resources (data, software, semantic artefacts), a certain harmonisation of the output formats of these tools is desirable. In particular, we investigated the use of existing formats and vocabularies, in particular the Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV) already mentioned above. In a dedicated document we defined an extended DQV model following the proposal of Radulovic (2015)⁵⁹ by using additional ontologies which are suited to cover the necessary FAIR requirements identified.

In detail the Quality Model Ontology (QMO) is useful which allows to relate metric dimensions with scales which are defined as subtypes of OM scales. To link these scales to individual FAIR measurements the Evaluation Result Ontology (EVAL)⁶⁰ is required additionally. Finally, the Evaluation and Report Language (EARL)⁶¹ is needed because it offers a controlled vocabulary for test outcomes including terms (e.g. ‘passed’, ‘failed’ or ‘inapplicable’). Finally, the Test Metadata Vocabulary (TEST)⁶² is required to specify test inputs, conditions and expected results which is suited to increase the overall transparency of a FAIR assessment.

A first draft of this model can be found here⁶³, as a pilot implementation the F-UJI tool has been modified to support the output of a serialisation of this model in various formats such as turtle, RDF XML or JSON-LD. In cooperation with the OStrails project⁶⁴, the model is currently being discussed and it is planned to use the model as input for a future simple FAIR output format.

2.5 Guidance Materials

The prototype will enable end users to find information about repositories that can support them in deciding whether the service is trustworthy. However, it is important that the prototype also provides users with some guidance or advice on assessing the content that is exposed. For example, if the prototype enables end users to find the preservation policy for

⁵⁹ Radulovic, Filip & Mihindukulasooriya, Nandana & García Castro, Raúl & Gomez-Perez, Asuncion. (2017). A comprehensive quality model for Linked Data. Semantic Web. 9. 1-22. 10.3233/SW-170267

⁶⁰ <http://purl.org/net/EvaluationResult#>

⁶¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/EARL10-Schema>

⁶² <https://www.w3.org/TR/test-metadata/>

⁶³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1SvxJuS2ekfnn4K8KB_BI_g7pc1qOt56YHrvTecxaccY/edit?usp=sharing

⁶⁴ <https://ostrails.eu/>

a given repository, the mere existence of the preservation policy does not in itself guarantee that a repository is trustworthy. It is the content of the policy that will determine the trustworthiness of the service. As such, FAIR-IMPACT will embed some high level guidance about how to interpret the information that is exposed by the prototype to better enable end users to make a more informed decision on the overall trustworthiness of the service. The guidance will be drawn from existing sources wherever possible (e.g., CoreTrustSeal).

3 Conclusions and next steps

This Milestone provides an update of the development of a pilot for exposing repository trustworthiness status and FAIR data and code assessment outcomes.

The initial prototype, as described in this document, focusses on a small set of relevant repository metadata properties indicated by the DRAWG. Beyond this, there is significant scope to expand these mechanisms to support both humans and machines in a wider variety of use cases.

The work on the prototype will be continued over the coming months and includes a second support offer in collaboration with Work Package 2 on Engagement, Adoption and Implementation⁶⁵. The support programme “*Exposing information about trustworthy and FAIR-enabling data repositories*” will start in January 2025. Repositories interested in increasing the findability and interoperability of their organisation by exposing machine actionable metadata about themselves and their datasets are invited to participate. They will receive support from the project to test the prototype. The findings from these tests will be used for a final iteration of the prototype.

⁶⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/apply-financial-support>

4 Appendix

URL lookup table for data services

Acronym	URI	Title	Type
OAI-PMH	https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/openarchivesprotocol.html	Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting	doc
OAI-PMH	http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/	Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting	namespace
Static OAI	https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/guidelines-static-repository.htm	OAI Static Repository	doc
REST	https://ics.uci.edu/~fielding/pubs/dissertation/rest_arch_style.htm	Representational State Transfer	doc
OpenDAP	https://docs.opendap.org/index.php/Home	OpenDAP	doc
THREDDS	https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/tds/	THREDDS Data Server	doc
ERDDAP	https://coastwatch.pfeg.noaa.gov/erddap/index.html	ERDDAP	doc
SPARQL	https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/	SPARQL Query Language	doc
SOAP	https://www.w3.org/TR/soap/	Simple Object Access Protocol	doc
SWORD	http://swordapp.org/	Simple Web-service Offering Repository Deposit	
Sitemaps	https://www.sitemaps.org/protocol.html	Sitemaps XML format	doc
OpenAPI	https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v3.1.0	OpenAPI Specification	doc
OpenAPI	https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v3.0.3	OpenAPI Specification	doc
OpenAPI	https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v2.0	OpenAPI Specification	doc
IIIF	https://iiif.io/api/presentation/3.0/	IIIF Presentation API	doc
LDN	https://www.w3.org/TR/ldn/	Linked Data Notifications	doc
OpenSearch	https://github.com/dewitt/opensearch/blob/master/opensearch-1-1-draft-6.md	Open Search	doc
OpenSearch	http://www.opensearch.org/Specifications/OpenSearch/1.1	Open Search	doc
OpenSearch	http://a9.com/-/spec/opensearch/1.1/	Open Search	namespace
RSS	https://www.rssboard.org/rss-specification	Really Simple Syndication	doc

FAIRiCat	https://signposting.org/FAIRiCat/	FAIRiCat: Supporting Discovery of a Repository's Interoperability Affordances	doc
LAS	https://ferret.pmel.noaa.gov/LAS/	Live Access Server	doc
AMPQ	https://www.amqp.org/resources/specifications	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol	doc
MQTT	https://mqtt.org/mqtt-specification/	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport	doc
XMPP	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc6120/	Extensible Messaging and Presence Protocol	doc
TAP	https://www.ivoa.net/documents/TAP/	Table Access Protocol	doc
TAPIR	https://www.tdwg.org/standards/tapir/	TDWG Access Protocol for Information Retrieval	doc
DIGIR	https://sourceforge.net/projects/digir/	Distributed Generic Information Retrieval	doc
DIGIR	http://digir.net/schema/protocol/2003/1.0	Distributed Generic Information Retrieval	namespace
CSW	http://www.opengis.net/def/serviceType/ogc/csw	OGC Catalogue Service for the Web	doc
CSW	https://www.ogc.org/standard/cat/	OGC Catalogue Service for the Web	doc
WMS	http://www.opengis.net/def/serviceType/ogc/wms	OGC Web Map Service	doc
WMS	http://www.ogc.org/standards/wms	OGC Web Map Service	doc
WMTS	https://www.ogc.org/standard/wmts/	OpenGIS Web Map Tile Service	doc
WFS	http://www.opengis.net/def/serviceType/ogc/wfs	OGC Web Feature Service	doc
WFS	http://www.ogc.org/standards/wfs	OGC Web Feature Service	doc
SOS	http://www.opengis.net/def/serviceType/ogc/sos	OGC Sensor Observation Service	doc
SOS	http://www.ogc.org/standards/sos	OGC Sensor Observation Service	doc
WCS	http://www.opengis.net/def/serviceType/ogc/wcs	OGC Web Coverage Service	doc
WCS	http://www.ogc.org/standards/wcs	OGC Web Coverage Service	doc